

EOSC-ENTRUST: Final TRE Survey 2026

Introduction to the survey

Thank you in advance for taking the time to respond to this survey by the EOSC-ENTRUST project's work on trusted research environment (referred to as TRE or 'environment' from here on) providers.

This survey is based on a survey done previously by HDRUK*, as well as the 2024 and 2025 surveys** by the EOSC-ENTRUST project.

Please read the questions carefully before answering. If you want to browse the questions before submitting responses, you can find a PDF version of the survey here: **LINK TO BE ADDED**

This survey takes approximately 30 minutes to complete in one sitting.

If a question is not applicable to the environment in question, it can be skipped. Only some of the questions regarding administrative information are mandatory in the survey. If the provider in question is operating several environments, it is advisable to answer the survey for all of them separately.

The survey closes at midnight CET on Tuesday, 30th June 2026. The deadline may be extended if needed.

*) <https://hdruk.github.io/TRE-Survey/>

***) The 2025 survey's findings were published in EOSC-ENTRUST MS11 Inventory & summary of updated TRE Provider capabilities: <https://zenodo.org/records/17035341>

Target audience

This survey is directed at all who identify themselves as trusted research environment providers or who are interested in being included in the EOSC ENTRUST TRE inventory. It is up to the providers to choose the most suitable individual experts to draft and submit the survey responses. We do not collect personal identifiers from the individuals submitting responses for this survey.

Purpose of survey

One of the EOSC-ENTRUST project's tasks is to create an inventory of TREs. This survey serves the purpose of the inventory, as well as capability mapping and gap analysis. The aim is also to collect initial sets of high-level requirements and best practices on TREs from providers. In addition, the outcomes will give input for the TRE blueprint to be developed by the EOSC-ENTRUST project. Based on the survey, a public TRE inventory will be published. Sensitive data on security measures will not be a part of the public inventory, rather these are stored as raw data for the ENTRUST project solely.

Use of answers

Answers will be used for the third and final iteration of the TRE inventory, which is one of EOSC-ENTRUST project's milestones. The inventory will be published on the project Zenodo repository (by the end of August 2026). The data will be managed and stored during the project and after the project according to the EOSC-ENTRUST project data management plan, consortium agreement, and other relevant project guidelines.

What do we mean by TRE in the context of this survey?

For the purpose of this survey, a trusted research environment (TRE) is any digital solution, or an interoperable collection of solutions, specifically intended for handling sensitive research data. There are other terms also in use for environments for handling sensitive data, such as secure processing environment (SPE) and data safe haven, etc. This survey is NOT intended only for those solutions that self-identify as TREs. The aim is to collect information from all and any environments for handling sensitive data by service providers.

About EOSC-ENTRUST

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) for sensitive data and drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis. The project brings together providers of operational TREs from 15 European countries with a shared goal to implement, validate and promote their capabilities through a common European framework using shared standards and common legal, operational and technical language. This blueprint for interoperability is anchored in the EOSC Interoperability Framework spanning the four dimensions of legal, organisational, technical and semantic interoperability. EOSC-ENTRUST has identified four driver projects covering genomics, clinical trials, social science and public private partnerships to benchmark capabilities, inform blueprint design and demonstrate secure data analysis using federated workflows.

Contact person for the survey

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* Indicates required question

Organisational details

Information about the organisation hosting the environment

1. Name of the environment *

2. Name of service provider *

3. [Organisation ROR](#)

4. Organisation two-letter [country code](#) *

5. What is the GDPR role of the organisation?

Mark only one oval.

Data controller

Data processor

Both

6. What is the organisation / business model?

Mark only one oval.

Financially independent

Depends on grants

Start up < 50% financially independent

Start up > 50% financially independent

Functional Capabilities

Description of the type of the environment and its main use cases

7. Please provide a service self-description

Tick all that apply.

- Trusted Research Environment (TRE)
- Secure Processing Environment (SPE)
- Data Safe Haven
- Remote access system
- Other: _____

8. What TRE service zones are present?

Tick all that apply.

- TRE/Research Analytics Zone
- TRE/Data Management Zone
- TRE/Data Query Zone

9. Is the environment available only for processing sensitive data use cases?

Mark only one oval.

- Dedicated to sensitive data
- Multi-purpose

10. Where is the data stored and processed?

Tick all that apply.

- On-prem
- Vendor-hosted
- Customer-hosted

11. What is the software deployment model?

Tick all that apply.

- Self-hosted
- On-prem
- Software-as-a-Service
- Hybrid

12. Who can use the environment?

Tick all that apply.

- Own organisation
- Academic / Research institutes nationally
- Academic / Research institutes internationally
- Industry

13. What scientific domains are served by the environment?

Tick all that apply.

- Agricultural Sciences
- Engineer & Technology
- Generic
- Humanities
- Medical & Health Sciences
- Natural Sciences
- Social Sciences
- Other

14. Please provide the URL for the service webpage *

15. Please provide a short service description

16. Indicate the languages the environment is available in using the [2-letter language code](#).

17. Is the environment available only for public benefit purposes?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

N/A

18. What is the environment TRL?

Mark only one oval.

TRL 9

TRL 8

TRL 7

TRL 6

N/A

19. Provide the helpdesk email

20. Provide the security contact email

Skip to question 21

Access mechanisms

Information about how access to the environment is enabled

21. Is there a self-service user login?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

22. Is there a two-factor authentication?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

23. Is there single sign-on?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

24. Is there enforced periodic access review?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

International Accessibility & Accepted Data Types

Referring to the accessibility of the environment, e.g. can it be accessed from EU countries, and information on which technical data types are accepted for import and export.

25. From which countries can the environment be accessed?

Mark only one oval.

Only national access possible

Access possible from EU and/or EEA countries

Global access possible

26. From what region can the PI be registered? A PI is here defined as the researcher who has primary responsibility for the research project.

Mark only one oval.

Only national registration possible

Registration possible from EU and/or EEA countries

Global registration possible

27. From what region can non-PI project members be registered?

Mark only one oval.

- Only national registration possible
- Registration possible from EU and/or EEA countries
- Global registration possible

28. Is there remote access to the environment?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Yes, copy/paste local/remote is disabled

29. What is used for the environment: on premise, private cloud, public cloud, or hybrid?

Mark only one oval.

- On premise
- Private
- Public
- Hybrid
- N/A

30. Are supported technical data types inside the environment restricted or unrestricted?

Mark only one oval.

- Unrestricted data types
- Restricted data types

31. If restricted, please list data types supported inside the environment. If unrestricted, move to next question.

32. Are technical data types for export restricted or unrestricted?

Mark only one oval.

- Unrestricted data types
- Restricted data types

33. If restricted, please list data types supported for export. If unrestricted, move to next question.

Auditing and Security Measures

Information on security measures taken to ensure the security of the environment.

34. Does the service have an ISO27001 certification?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

35. Does the service have a NIS 2 certification?

Mark only one oval.

No

Yes, SC-10

Yes, SC-20

Yes, SC-30

N/A (Environment is not within EU jurisdiction)

36. Are there other security audits and certificates?

Tick all that apply.

National

Regional

Organisational

Other: _____

37. Please list other security audits and certificates.

38. Are project areas fully isolated from each other?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

39. If yes, how are project areas isolated from each other?

40. What are the security measures against unauthorised access?

Tick all that apply.

- AAI
- AAAI
- Multi Factor Authentication
- Periodic access review
- Role-based access control
- Federated user accounts
- Individual identification (e.g. passport check)
- Other: _____

41. What are the security measures for mitigating data loss?

Tick all that apply.

- Data backup
- Snapshots
- User guidelines
- Cybersecurity measures
- Other: _____

42. What are the security measures for mitigating misuse by users?

Tick all that apply.

- Authorised access
- Activity logs
- Export encryptions
- Sanctions
- Certifications
- User restrictions
- User training
- Other: _____

Computing and Analysis Services

Computing and analysis services available for the user, such as information on the operating system, analysis software and tools available

43. What is the standard base operating system?

Tick all that apply.

- Windows
- Linux-based (Ubuntu, Rocky, etc.)
- Other: _____

44. Which specific operating system is used?

Tick all that apply.

- Windows
- Linux
- Ubuntu
- Rocky
- Unix
- Redhat Enterprise
- CentOS Stream
- Other: _____

45. What operating systems are available to users?

Tick all that apply.

- Windows
- Linux-based
- Other: _____

46. Is there access to HPC in/through the environment?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

47. What kind of tooling is provided?

Tick all that apply.

- Self-service any
- Self-service restricted
- Serviced any
- Serviced restricted

48. If tooling is restricted, please list the supported applications. If unrestricted, move onto the next question.

49. Is there support for AI/machine learning?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

50. If yes, how is AI/ML support set up? If no, move onto the next question.

Tick all that apply.

Within the project environment

As a service controlled by the organisation / consortium

Public ML/AI

51. What processing types are available?

Tick all that apply.

CPU

GPU

TPU

52. What processing conditions are in place?

Tick all that apply.

- Pay-per-use
- Available-on-demand
- Reserved

User Rights

What rights and restrictions does the user have in the environment, e.g. can own packages be installed?

53. Are users allowed to import code/software/libraries?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- N/A

54. What is the user import source?

Tick all that apply.

- Clipboard
- Unregulated network access
- Network access regulated by TRE
- Network access regulated by external entity
- Self-upload
- Data holder upload
- Other: _____

55. What is the user import type?

Tick all that apply.

- Any
- Text only
- Source code
- Containers
- Data
- Other: _____

56. What data storage is available?

Mark only one oval.

- <1TB
- <5TB
- <25TB
- <50TB
- <100TB
- <200TB
- >200TB

57. What is the maximum data storage available?

Mark only one oval.

- <1TB
- <5TB
- <25TB
- <50TB
- <100TB
- <200TB
- >200TB

58. What type of data storage is used?

Mark only one oval.

- SMP
- Blob

59. What is the user import connection?

Mark only one oval.

- Unregulated
- Encrypted
- Limited to stated internal addresses
- Limited to any stated address
- Other:

60. What conditions are there on users importing code/software/libraries?

Mark only one oval.

- No restrictions
- Imports are checked - automated
- Imports are checked - manual
- Sampling - automated (some imports checked)
- Sampling - manual (some imports checked)
- No imports by users

61. What is the user export type?

Tick all that apply.

- Any
- Text only
- Source code
- Containers
- Data
- Other: _____

62. What measures are there against malicious code execution?

Tick all that apply.

- Antivirus checks for all imports
- Regular monitoring
- Restrictions on route access
- Other: _____

Data Discovery, Federated Analysis and Architecture

This section asks about the availability of a public discovery service for datasets, if support for federated analysis is provided, and a description of the architecture the environment is based on

63. Is there a public discovery service for datasets available in this TRE?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

64. If yes, please provide a link to the public discovery service

65. Does the service support federated queries?

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Work in progress

66. If federated queries are supported, what technology is used for this? If not supported, please move to the next question.

67. Does the service support federated queries of metadata/data from external authorised users?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Work in progress

68. Does the environment follow a specific reference architecture?

Mark only one oval.

- SATRE
- National reference architecture
- Institutional reference architecture
- EOSC ENTRUST Blueprint
- Other:

EOSC and EHDS alignment

This final section asks about the environment's alignment with major European initiatives (EOSC and EHDS).

69. Do you see your environment being a part of EOSC offerings in the future?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Undecided
- N/A (environment is non-European)

70. How do you intend to approach EOSC integration, if applicable?

Mark only one oval.

- Become a node
- As part of service offerings on a national node
- As part of service offerings on a thematic (i.e. disciplinary-specific) node
- As part of service offerings on multiple nodes
- Other:

71. What support do you require for EOSC integration?

Tick all that apply.

- Onboarding guidelines
- Support in identifying the right node(s) for the environment
- Information on the Node Exchange (i.e. the use of services across nodes)
- Other: _____

72. Have you started collaboration with local authorities for EHDS alignment?

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

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